

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Mbelolo****FIRST NAME: Chancellor****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 4%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is the most crucial factor to consider when choosing to conduct qualitative research?

- To get the best from conducting any qualitative research, you need to focus on the quality of answers.¹**
- You need also to focus on the number of respondents.
- Qualitative data is focused on the quantity of information obtained.
- Qualitative research is based on dissertation structure.

¹Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 135.

2. What is the methodology of the research approach?
- Developing your methodology involves studying the research methods used in your field and the theories or principles that underpin them, in order to choose the approach that best matches your objectives.²**
 - The overarching rationale of your research doesn't refer to the methodology.
 - We don't need to justify the methodological choices we made.
 - Introducing instruments is enough when writing an effective methodology section.
3. What involves collecting both quantitative and qualitative data and integrating the two forms of data?
- This study design combines quantitative research design and qualitative research design. Mixed methods research involves collecting quantitative and qualitative data, and analysis of the data integrates both forms of data.³**
 - You can't use the two methodologies together to gain deeper insight into particular questions.
 - Furthermore, researchers can't use these methods concurrently or sequentially.
 - Quantitative and qualitative data can't become interdependent in addressing common research questions and hypotheses.

² Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 435-447.

³ Sampson, James P. Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. (College of Education: Florida State University 2017), 7-10.

4. What makes a successful dissertation?

You should be able to justify every choice you make in your dissertation. There should be good, academic reasons for your choice of focus, of reading, of methodology, and of analytical techniques. Know why you did things the way you did, and make sure your reader knows why, too.⁴

Review literature is the only element of an effective dissertation.

A successful dissertation needs to identify appropriately, the primary and secondary sources.

Keywords are not necessary to use in the concept of your dissertation.

5. How do you make your dissertation ‘speak’ to experts?

You can assume your expert reader will have some background understanding of the research methods, and general knowledge relevant to your topic.⁵

By highlighting the most significant results.

By interpreting the results.

By providing recommendations for further research.

⁴ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 10-16.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 21–22.

6. What makes a source reliable and relevant?

It is essential to be able to identify which sources are credible. This ability requires an understanding of depth, objectivity, currency, authority, and purpose. Whether or not your source is peer-reviewed, it is still a good idea to evaluate it.⁶

All sources are credible.

There is no method to evaluate a source.

All referenced materials are reliable and relevant.

7. What is the description of the dissertation project?

The dissertation is a critical review of the literature that addresses the major question, or series of questions, relevant to your research topic. It is important that it conveys the current state of knowledge on the topic to the reader as clearly, concisely, and convincingly as possible.⁷

Topic, question, problem, working hypothesis.

A clear conceptual framework anchors your research in the context of known models and established theories used by scholars in your field.

Theoretical underpinnings used to frame research in your field.

⁶ Ibid., 41-43.

⁷ Ibid., 23-35.

8. What does it mean to construct an argument?

The argument is based on your reading of a text. This means you should express ideas about a text that others in your class may not have considered. You might even express ideas that others disagree with (as long as you can offer evidence in support).⁸

Acknowledging the opposing side of the answer or hypothesis.

Connecting logically series of statements.

Assuming the results and the conclusion.

9. How do you cite in-text writing?

When using APA format, follow the author-date method of in-text citation. This means that the author's last name, the year of publication, and the page number of the source should appear, all in parentheses.⁹

Putting the Author's full name and the area of publication in parentheses.

Using the author's last name and year of publication of the source in italics.

Use the author's name, year of publication, and the title of the source, all in quotation marks.

⁸ Turabian, 56-67.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 35.

10. What is a direct quote in a research paper?

- A direct quote is when you take another person's words and place them in your own document. These must always be placed inside quotation marks and given appropriate attribution (APA, Chicago, etc.).¹⁰**
- Quoted material should or not be reproduced word-by-word
- When using direct quotes, constantly reproduce the author's full name.
- Taking an idea or fact from a second source is a direct quotation.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Eighth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Sampson, James P. Jr. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Ed. College of Education: Florida State University, 2017.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

¹⁰ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 36-39.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.